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The Hidden Treasure: The Role of Darts in Acquisition of Mathematical Concepts

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Research Article

The Hidden Treasure: The Role of Darts in Acquisition of Mathematical Concepts

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ABSTRACT

This study set out to explore the role of darts in acquisition of mathematical concepts. A case study was carried out in Mucheke Suburb, Masvingo Province, in Zimbabwe. Twenty participants (18 males and 2 females) from two teams in Masvingo District Darts Association were purposely selected to take part in the study. The researchers used interviews and participant observation to gather data since they also play for one of the teams studied. This study found out that darts are very useful in facilitating the acquisition of cognitive skills like addition, subtraction, multiplication and division. Players also acquire skills in carrying out combined operations and idiosyncratic algorithms. Besides acquiring cognitive skills, players also acquire psychomotor skills which improve their precision in target hitting. In the process of play, the researchers noted that individuals' emotional skills develop as evidenced by virtues of tolerance, cooperation and acceptance of criticism. Irrespective of these benefits, the researchers noted that darts still remain a hidden treasure since they are mostly played in pubs with limited access to children and most of those who do not take alcohol. Arising from the findings were recommendations that, women and children should be given access to play darts since they are useful in mathematics education as well as human development.

Keywords: darts, mathematics, cognitive development, psychomotor development, emotional development.

INTRODUCTION AND OVERVIEW

Mathematics enables individuals to participate fully in a society which is saturated with quantitative and technological information (Arora, 1995; Alausa, 2000). Irrespective of its importance, mathematics education in Zimbabwe poses numerous challenges like mathophobia, persistent dropout rates and catastrophic pass rates. Previous studies on the nature of mathematics education in Zimbabwe (Dhliwayo, 1998; Nyagura, 1991; Nziramasanga, 1998) indicate that limited resources, lack of opportunities and experiences, hinder pupils' access to excellent mathematics instructional programs. Giving pupils a variety of resources and experiences enables them to acquire cognitive, psychomotor and emotional skills which are necessary in mathematics education (Bloom, cited in Petty, 2009). One way by which students acquire mathematical skills is through play (Isenberg and Jalongo, 1993; Mosimanga, 2000; Robertson, 2001). The four basic operations, that is, addition, subtraction, multiplication and division which form the bedrock of mathematical knowledge can be best acquired through playing darts. Several studies on the role of play in education (Wolfgang and Wolfgang, 1992; Mosimanga, 2000) have been carried out, but they were too general. This study explores a specific game (darts) and how it facilitates acquisition of specific mathematical skills in depth. It is unique in the sense that it integrates knowledge in both Mathematics and Physical Education.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study was guided by Benjamin Bloom's Theory of Taxonomy of Educational Objectives. In 1948, groups of Psychologists interested in achievement testing met at an American Psychology Association Convention in Boston. The deliberations in this convention gave birth to classification (taxonomy) of learning objectives that could guide effective assessment. These learning objectives also guide in understanding the style in which individuals learn. Bloom cited in Petty (2009) posits that individuals learn in three styles namely cognitive, psychomotor and effective patterns. The cognitive style involves perceiving and thinking, which an individual exhibits in problem solving.

Example includes how to add, subtract or multiply. It also involves remembering or reproducing something which has been presumably learned, combining and synthesizing new ideas.

Psychomotor learning, emphasizes some muscular or motor skills and some manipulation of material and objects and some action which require neuro-muscular coordination. Affective style of learning is associated with a feeling of interest, tone, emotions, attitude, appreciation, cooperation and temperamental characteristics. This theoretical framework was found most appropriate because the game of darts involves calculations, throwing, target hitting, cooperation and pleasure.

Statement of the Problem

Darts facilitate the acquisition of cognitive, psychomotor and emotional skills which form the basis in understanding mathematical concepts yet they are usually played in pubs with limited access to children and most of those who do not take alcohol.

Major Research Question

To what extent does the game of darts facilitate the acquisition of skills necessary in mathematics education?

Sub-Research Questions

How do darts facilitate the acquisition of cognitive skills?

To what extent do darts facilitate the acquisition of psychomotor skills?

How do darts facilitate the acquisition of affective skills?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employed a case study design in which the researcher involved participants (18 males and 2 females) from two teams in Masvingo District Darts Association. The participants were interviewed to provide answers to research questions. The researchers also used participant observation since they also play darts for the local league. The data obtained was analyzed using qualitative interpretational analysis. Interpretational analysis is the process of examining data closely in order to find constructs, themes and explain phenomenon (Borg, Gall and Borg, 1996).

Population and Sample

The two clubs from which the sample was drawn had forty registered players (38 males and 2 females). The researchers purposely selected twenty (18 males and 2 females) who responded to interview questions.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

The findings of this study appear in four categories in which answers to research questions are provided. The categories comprise:

- (a) The role of darts in acquisition of cognitive skills.
- (b) The role of darts in acquisition of psychomotor skills.
- (c) The role of darts in acquisition of affective skills.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The role of darts in acquisition of cognitive skills

The researchers noted that darts improve cognitive skills through number identification, addition, multiplication, subtraction and division. Players also master combined operations as well as the concepts of factors and multiples.

Number Identification

The nature of the game requires players to identify the number and the positions they want to play because the numbers on the dart board are not ordered as shown on fig 1 below:-

Fig 1: The Dart Board

Besides identifying the position and number they want to play, the players also need to remember these for future play. All twenty respondents indicated that the most common positions to be remembered by new players are the Bulls' Eye and the sector number 20. The rest of the positions and numbers are mastered after repeated practice. For example, if one needs to hit an odd number, simply throws an arrow to the lower left side in the board where there are 7; 19; 3 and 17. If one needs to hit an even number simply throws either to the middle right for 6 and 10 or to the middle left for 16 and 8. The researcher noted that number identification was a primary skill upon which other mathematical skills rested upon.

Learning simple addition

Darts are played in such a way that players aim big numbers with 3 arrows. The points are added and subtracted cumulatively from say, 1001, 701, 501, or 301. The first player to reduce to zero with the closing arrow hitting the doubles ring or the bull's eye is the winner. In the process of play researchers noted that one's addition is improved and perfected for example if one is reducing aiming the sector with 20 he/she is likely to hit the following singles:

20; 20; 20 = 60
 20; 20; 1 = 41
 20; 20; 5 = 45
 20; 1; 5 = 26
 1; 1; 1 = 3
 5; 5; 5 = 15
 5; 5; 1 = 11
 20; 5; 12 = 37
 5; 1; 1 = 7

Continuous practice enables the players to simply observe the arrangement or position of arrows and quickly add within seconds.

Multiplication skills

The dart board is divided into singles, doubles and triples spaces as indicated on fig, 1, if one hits the singles space the number hit is multiplied by 1, for the doubles ring (D) number hit is multiplied by 2 and for the triples ring (T) the number is multiplied by 3. By hitting the doubles ring (D) players master multiplication of numbers 1 to 20 by 2, for example:

$1 \times 2 = 2$	$6 \times 2 = 12$	$11 \times 2 = 22$	$16 \times 2 = 32$
$2 \times 2 = 4$	$7 \times 2 = 14$	$12 \times 2 = 24$	$17 \times 2 = 34$
$3 \times 2 = 6$	$8 \times 2 = 16$	$13 \times 2 = 26$	$18 \times 2 = 36$
$4 \times 2 = 8$	$9 \times 2 = 18$	$14 \times 2 = 28$	$19 \times 2 = 38$
$5 \times 2 = 10$	$10 \times 2 = 20$	$15 \times 2 = 30$	$20 \times 2 = 40$

Hitting the triples ring also enables the players to master multiplication of numbers 1 to 20 by 3, for example:

$1 \times 3 = 3$	$6 \times 3 = 18$	$11 \times 3 = 33$	$16 \times 3 = 48$
$2 \times 3 = 6$	$7 \times 3 = 21$	$12 \times 3 = 36$	$17 \times 3 = 51$
$3 \times 3 = 9$	$8 \times 3 = 24$	$13 \times 3 = 39$	$18 \times 3 = 54$
$4 \times 3 = 12$	$9 \times 3 = 27$	$14 \times 3 = 42$	$19 \times 3 = 57$
$5 \times 3 = 15$	$10 \times 3 = 30$	$15 \times 3 = 45$	$20 \times 3 = 60$

Division skills

The game is closed when one reduces the number to zero by hitting the doubles ring (D) or the bull's eye for example when one is left with 40, he or she has to close using the doubles ring (D). This requires dividing the points by 2 and then hitting the doubles ring, in this case a player divides 40 by 2 and then hits double 20 (D20). Other examples in which one masters division skills at closing point are:

38 by D19	26 by D13	14 by D7
36 by D18	24 by D12	12 by D6
34 by D17	22 by D11	10 by D5
32 by D16	20 by D10	8 by D4
30 by D15	18 by D9	6 by D3
28 by D14	16 by D8	4 by D2
2 by D1		

Combined operations

In most cases the players have to be engaged in combined operations when play is in progress for example the researchers noted that the players would add, multiply and then subtract. Suppose one reduces from 1001 by targeting the sector with 20 he/she is likely to score 20, D20 and T20. In this case the points scored = $20 + (20 \times 2) + (20 \times 3) = 20 + 40 + 60 = 120$. If subtracted from 1001 the player remains with 881 points. Here are some examples in which players master combined operations when reducing from 1001:

SCORING SEQUENCE	ADDITION SEQUENCE	TOTAL SCORE	REMAINING SCORE
20 T20 20	$20 + (20 \times 3) + 20$	100	901
20 T1 20	$20 + (1 \times 3) + 20$	43	958
T20 T20 T20	$(20 \times 3) + (20 \times 3) + (20 \times 3)$	180	821
T5 T5 D20	$(5 \times 3) + (5 \times 3) + (2 \times 20)$	70	931
19 T19 D19	$19 + (19 \times 3) + (2 \times 19)$	114	887
T20 Bull D20	$(20 \times 3) + 50 + (2 \times 20)$	150	851
3 T19 19	$3 + (19 \times 3) + 19$	79	921
T20 T19 D19	$(20 \times 3) + (19 \times 3) + (19 \times 2)$	155	846

As play progresses, and with continuous practice, researchers noted that players were likely to encounter more situations which require combined operations and would carry them perfectly. Players also encountered combined operations when closing even numbers. Most of the even numbers below 170 are closable using only 3 arrows. In this process, combined operations are involved in which one has to add, multiply, subtract and divide. For example if one wants to close 160, he/she can hit T20 and T20 using the first two arrows to score 120. The remainder of 40 from 160 is closable using the doubles ring. This requires division by two to identify the closing point in this case D20. Here are some examples of using combined operations in closing even numbers:

CLOSABLE EVEN NUMBERS	SCORING AND CLOSING SEQUENCE
170	T20 T20 Bull
164	T20 T18 Bull
160	T20 T20 D20
158	T20 T20 D19
156	T20 T20 D18
154	T20 T18 D20 or T20 T20 D17
140	T20 D20 D20
100	T20 D20 or 20 D20 D20
80	T20 D10 or D20 D20 or 20 20 D20
52	12 D20
42	2 D20

In the process of play, players were likely to encounter a situation where they have to close odd numbers. The game is over if one reduces the remaining number to zero using the doubles ring (D). This implies that an odd number cannot be closed by one arrow. A player needs 2 to 3 arrows depending on the magnitude of the numbers. One has to perform the task of shaping before closing an odd number. That is to hit an odd number so that an even number remains for example if a player has 37, shaping can be done by hitting the lower left side in the board with sectors of odd numbers 7; 19; 3; 11 and then closing using the doubles ring (D) for example:

7 for D15
 19 for D9
 3 for D17
 17 for D10

Shaping can also be involved in combined operations when dealing with large odd numbers, for example, when closing 167, players can close using the sequence T20 – T19 (shaping arrow/score), Bull. Here are some examples in which the second score plays the shaping role:

CLOSABLE ODD NUMBERS	SCORING SEQUENCE INCLUDING SHAPING
161	T20 T17 Bull
157	T20 T19 D20
155	T20 T19 D19
153	T20 T19 D18
151	T20 T12 D20
149	T20 T19 D16
101	T17 Bull
95	T19 D19
57	19 D19
41	1 D20 or 3 D19 or 19 D11

Combined idiosyncratic algorithms

In the process of play, the researchers noted that, players can develop idiosyncratic algorithms, that is, their own way of carrying out the basic operations for example when subtracting a number from 1001, they would first subtract the score from 1000 or 100 and then add 1 since subtracting from 1000 or 100 is easy, for instance, a score of 50 would leave 950 + 1 which is 951. Other examples of subtracting from 1001 noted using the same way were as follows:

SCORE	SUBTRACTING FROM 1001	REMAINING SCORE
100	$(1000 - 100)+1$	901
90	$(1000- 90)+1$	911
56	$(1000 - 56)+1$	945
7	$(1000 - 7)+1$	994
3	$(1000 - 3)+1$	998

When subtracting a number below 100, the researchers noted that players would subtract 100 and add the difference from 100 for example;

$$721 - 99 = (721 - 100) + 1 = 622$$

$$721 - 98 = (721 - 100) + 2 = 623$$

$$721 - 95 = (721 - 100) + 5 = 626$$

$$721 - 90 = (721 - 100) + 10 = 631$$

$$721 - 50 = (721 - 100) + 50 = 671$$

$$721 - 48 = (721 - 100) + 52 = 663$$

$$721 - 27 = (721 - 100) + 73 = 694$$

When adding numbers researchers noted that players used to add the nearest large number which ends with a zero and then subtract the difference as shown in examples below:

$$23 + 48 = (23+50)-2 = 71$$

$$23 + 97 = (23+100)-3=120$$

$$23 + 59 = (23+60)-1 = 82$$

$$23 + 95 = (23+100)-5 = 118$$

When closing a number, researchers realized that players also employed idiosyncratic algorithms. Suppose a player wants to close 38 that is D19 and misses the target and hits D3, because of proximity, instead of determining the remaining house by saying

$38 - (3 \times 2) = 38 - 6 = 32 = D16$. They often said $D19 - D3 = D16$. Other examples are as follows:

TARGET	HOUSE HIT	REMAINING HOUSE
40 (D20)	D5	$D20 - D5 = D15$
40 (D20)	D1	$D20 - D1 = D19$
36 (D18)	D4	$D18 - D4 = D14$
30 (D15)	D2	$D15 - D2 = D13$
28 (D14)	D9	$D14 - D9 = D5$
36 (D18)	D1	$D18 - D1 = D17$

The same algorithms were also found to be employed when players were targeting the triples' ring so as to close with the second arrow for example, to close 100 they targeted T20 for D20 but in the event of missing it and hitting T1 they would quickly go to T19 for D20. Other noted examples were as follows:

1 st TARGET	TRIPPLE HIT	ALTERNATE TARGET
T20	T5	T15
T18	T1	T17
T16	T8	T8
T19	T7	T12
T18	T14	T14

Factors and multiples

Besides learning the four basic operations, the researchers also found out that the darts are useful in understanding the concepts of factors and multiples for example when reducing using the sector with 20 and one scores T20 with

the sequence 20 – T20 – T20 then 20, 40 and 60 are some of the factors of 120 which is also a multiple of 20; 40 and 60. Other factors and multiples and the sequences involved are as shown below:

MULTIPLE	SCORING SEQUENCE	FACTORS INVOLVED
114	19 D19 T19	19; 38 and 57
108	18 D18 T18	18; 36 and 54
102	17 D17 T17	17; 34 and 51
96	16 D16 T16	16; 32 and 48
90	15 D15 T15	15; 30 and 45

THE ROLE OF DARTS IN LEARNING PSYCHOMOTOR SKILLS

The researchers discovered that besides learning cognitive skills, players also acquire a great deal of psychomotor skills that is neuro-muscular coordination. The game requires precision in target shooting. In this case they acquire aiming and throwing skills. In throwing, they were usually guided by the “aim-hold and shoot principle”. The shooting principle was also guided by hand-eye coordination where they hold an arrow to be thrown at eye level.

Besides combining operations as in acquisition of cognitive skills, the researchers noted that players were also using their arrows in combination for example, in grouping. In the process of grouping, all the three arrows have to hit the board as close to each other as possible. When the first arrow is thrown, it is then used as the target to which other two arrows are thrown closer. Grouping was normally used when targeting the highest score that is T20; T20; T20 = 180. It was also used when closing 100 that is Bull; Bull. Other situations when players used the grouping skill in closing using two arrows were noted as follows:

TARGET HOUSE

60
57
54
51
3
45

GROUPING SEQUENCE

20 D20
19 D19
18 D18
17 D17
1 D1
15 D15

Shooting skills were also found useful in shaping and targeting even numbers. In shaping, they would simply throw an arrow targeting a group of odd numbers on the lower left side of the board where there is 7; 19; 3 and 17. When reducing by an even number to a closable house, they would simply target adjacent sectors like 10 and 6 or 16 and 8. For instance when closing 42, the sectors with 10 and 6 would give the following options:

10 for D16
6 for D18
D6 for D15
D10 for D11
T6 for D12
T10 for D6

Closely associated with grouping was the skill of using two arrows to guide the third arrow to a high score or to close a house, for example if the first arrow hits 20 just above T20 and the second hits 20 just below T20, these two arrows would then be used as guiding objects to hit T20. The same applies when closing 60, if the first arrow hits 20 just below D20 and the second arrow goes out of the board close to D20, then the two arrows act as guiding objects to close D20.

THE ROLE OF DARTS IN EMOTIONAL DEVELOPMENT

Eighteen (90%) of the participants indicated that they played for entertainment and socialization with peers. The researchers noted that this game plays a significant role in emotional development with team work. The players used to play in triples (2 teams of 3 players from each side) or doubles. Such team work enabled cooperation, tolerance, encouragement, motivation and acceptance of criticism which are very useful skills even in mathematics

education. The researchers also noted that both team work and individual work also resulted in the acceptance of defeat and respect for other competitors' rights.

CONCLUSION

From the findings discussed above, the researchers noted that darts are useful in cognitive, psychomotor and emotional development of the players yet limited individuals have access to this game. These groups exclude most children, women and those who do not go into pubs.

In cognitive development, the researchers noted that players gained skills in number identification, addition, subtraction, multiplication, division and combined operations. They also managed to gain knowledge on factors and multiples. As a way of improving their speed in calculations, they also developed useful and reliable idiosyncratic algorithms, that is, their own way of doing combined operations.

Closely related to cognitive development, players were also improving in their psychomotor skills (neuro-muscular coordination). These included aiming, shooting, hand-eye coordination, grouping and arrow guiding. These skills were used in combination with the cognitive mathematical skills indicated before.

The researchers also noted that darts also improve players' emotional development. They learned how to respect the rights and ideas of their team mates and opponents. They also learned to accept defeat and the competence of their teammates and opponents. In fact, they learned cooperation, tolerance and respect for others which are very important emotional skills in mathematics education.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Schools should shun the ill-conceived notion that darts are associated with alcohol consumption and introduce the game to the learners so as to enjoy its positive benefits.
- Other play centres should introduce this game so that it is not only limited to pubs which limit access to some groups.
- More women should also be given chance to play this useful game since the study indicates that their access is limited.
- Children should also be exposed to darts under the guidance of the mature experts to minimize injuries and maximize their positive benefits.

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